

Effectiveness Of Comprehensive Fall Prevention Protocol On Fall Risk In Elderly

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 24, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: October 25, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Comprehensive Fall Prevention Protocol, Fall, Fall Risk, Older Population, Berg Balance Scale and Functional Reach Test.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7246023</p>	<p>Background: Fall is a major problem in elder population. There are more than 12.13 Million older adults whose age is 60 years or above & by 2025 it will be 17.53 Million (1). 30-50% adults of age 60 & above have some problem with balance So large population is at risk to fall- (2).</p> <p>Objective: This study is aimed to determine effectiveness of comprehensive fall prevention protocol on fall risk in comparison of traditional/conventional treatment. Prevention of fall is important for well being of this age group and is also a challenge to rehabilitation department.</p> <p>Methods: Forty participants were allocated randomly through concealed envelope method to comprehensive fall prevention protocol & conventional balance training group i.e. twenty participants in each group. All participants of age 60-80 years were assessed at baseline through Berg Balance Scale, Functional Reach Test and post-intervention assessments were done after 4th, 8th, 12th & 24th week.</p> <p>Results: Results show that comprehensive fall prevention protocol reduces fall risk significantly as compared to traditional /conventional balance training because p-value is less than .05 that indicates significant difference.</p> <p>Conclusions: Comprehensive fall prevention protocol is better treatment than conventional balance training to reduce fall risk in elderly population.</p>

Introduction

Fall is a major problem in elderly population that leads to injury that cause psychological, social and physical impairment (3). According to the World Health Organization incidence of fall in aging population is from 28-35% of elder aged 65 & above, increases to 32-42% for those over 70 years (4). Fall episode leads to the fear of fall, limited mobility, loss of independence, hospitalization and may be death (5). Balance is an ability to maintain its line of gravity within the base of support with minimal postural sway. Sway is the horizontal movement of baseline due to small perturbations due to breathing, shifting of weight from one leg to other or upper limb movement during walking or due to external distractions. Sway increases with aging (3). Multiple systems work to keep body staying inside limits of mobility through auditory, sensorimotor, visual, vestibular and nervous system. Vestibular system maintain the balance of the body according to the position of the body (6). Sensorimotor system regulates balance through proprioception and kinesthetic sense (7). Visual system through verticality of body and head position (8). Nervous system coordinates all these information and maintain body balance (9).

All the studies conducted so far studied only one or two aspects of balance training. i.e. strength training with aerobic exercises to reduce fall risk and improve balance (10), to assess the effects of resisted exercise with flexibility on fall risk & Balance of elderly (11), Cognitive therapy with walking improves balance (12). Current study is focused to develop a comprehensive fall prevention protocol to address all the aspects of balance training. It includes cognitive therapy to help replace destructive & negative thoughts toward himself and world that leads to lower self-esteem, anxiety, decrease relationship and less expectations with positive thinking improved self-esteem relations and expectations. It also motivates to try new things. Progressive resisted exercise of antigravity muscles that starts from low intensity to higher intensities that are responsible for erect posture & balance (13). Aerobic exercise includes walking on a treadmill on ground with warm up and cool down periods self-stretching and active range of motion exercises of body (14). Exergaming improves balance through different games initially participants maintain good posture in static position i.e. head, upper limb, hip and lower limb position and equal body weight shifting on both lower limbs (15).

After that participant has to move him/her self from right to left, from front to backward and vice versa to save himself from different hurdles and at the same time to maintain his /her center of gravity to continue game. Initially there are less difficult levels then as participants balance improves it moves to more difficult

levels(16).Italso help to improve attention(17).Exergaming is interactive, emerging and entertaining form of exercise that have the ability to involve older adults and it improves cognitive and physical function through increase sensorial flow and motor functions(18).

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Total 40 older adult fulfilling the inclusion criteria were included in study 20 participants in interventional group (comprehensive fall prevention protocol)and 20 participants in the conventional group (control group) were assigned randomly through sealed envelope method. Inclusion criteria includes older adult of age between 60-80 years of either gender and Berg Balance Scale score 20-40.The exclusion criteria include participants suffering from musculoskeletal conditionsi.e.fractures, severe arthritis, neurological disease like epilepsy, Parkinson disease, Alzheimer’s disease impaired cognitive and other systematic diseasesor co morbidities that can effect balance.

There was no difference in demographics and clinical data at baseline in both groups

Procedures:

Berg Balance Scale’s score range of 20-40 was assessment criteria to enroll participants after meeting eligibility criteria in this study. The participants were randomly assigned in 2 groups interventional and conventionaland then Berg Balance Scale andFunctional Reach Test were used for the assessment of fall risk and severity of balance problem at baseline andeach follow-up of both conventional and interventional groups. The study was approved by Research Ethical Committee, Institutional Review Board and Board of Advanced Studies and Research Isra University, Islamabad Pakistan. The protocol of study was registered on National Library of Medicine (NCT04529200).

Intervention:

Session duration 40-45 minutes on alternate days
60% 1RM – 2sets*10 repetitions from 1 st to 2 nd week
65% 1RM – 2sets*10 repetitions from 3 rd to 4 th week
70% 1RM – 2sets*10 repetitions from 5 th to 6 th week
75% 1RM – 2sets*10 repetitions from 7 th to 8 th week

Ankle weights were used for strengthening of hip flexors, extensors, abductors, knee flexors and extensors, ankle dorsiflexors and plantar flexors and then same resisted exercise protocols was repeated till end(19).Cognitive therapy: - counselling of participant to help replace destructive & negative thoughts toward himself and world that leads to lower self-esteem, anxiety, decrease relationship and less expectations with positive thinking improved self-esteem relations and expectations(20).Treadmill was used for aerobic exercises with low speed and less inclination depending upon the ability of participant. Treadmill speed and inclination is increased as ability of participant is improved(21).

Older adult keeps the CoG static to continue the game during exergaming initially and then participant has to move in different direction to save from hurdles to continue game and at same time has to maintain balance. At each successive level of game,hurdles and speed of game increases and difficult to maintain the balance. Conventional group received Manual Internal/external protuberance, Strength training, Bosu ball and wobble board exercises(22).

Outcome measure:

Outcomes were assessed once before start ofintervention and after 4th, 8th, 12th and 24th week through Berg Balance Scale(23)and Functional Reach Test(FRT)(24). The procedure of all outcome measurements was completed within the same setting where baseline measurements of participants were recorded.

Statistical analysis:

Group Statistics, MANOVA and Repeated Measure ANOVA test were used to compare means of Berg Balance Scale score and Functional Reach Test score at baseline and after 4th, 8th, 12th and 24th weeks.

Table 1.1: MANOVA analysis of Berg Balance Scale

Pairwise Comparisons							
Dependent Variable	(I) study group of subjects	(J) study group of subjects	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Berg Balance Score 1	conventional group	care group	-2.800	1.457	.062	-5.750	.150
	care group	conventional group	2.800	1.457	.062	-.150	5.750
Berg Balance Score 2	conventional group	care group	-3.750 [*]	1.333	.008	-6.448	-1.052
	care group	conventional group	3.750 [*]	1.333	.008	1.052	6.448
Berg Balance Score 3	conventional group	care group	-9.050 [*]	.977	.000	-11.028	-7.072
	care group	conventional group	9.050 [*]	.977	.000	7.072	11.028
Berg Balance Score 4	conventional group	care group	-9.450 [*]	.941	.000	-11.356	-7.544
	care group	conventional group	9.450 [*]	.941	.000	7.544	11.356
Berg Balance Score 5	conventional group	care group	-10.700 [*]	.623	.000	-11.961	-9.439
	care group	conventional group	10.700 [*]	.623	.000	9.439	11.961

Table 2.4: MANOVA analysis of Functional Reach Test

Pairwise Comparisons							
Dependent Variable	(I) study group of subjects	(J) study group of subjects	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Functional reach test 1	conventional group	care group	-.555 [*]	.264	.042	-1.090	-.020
	care group	conventional group	.555 [*]	.264	.042	.020	1.090
Functional reach test 2	conventional group	care group	-.690 [*]	.266	.014	-1.229	-.151
	care group	conventional group	.690 [*]	.266	.014	.151	1.229
Functional reach test 3	conventional group	care group	-.770 [*]	.274	.008	-1.324	-.216
	care group	conventional group	.770 [*]	.274	.008	.216	1.324
Functional reach test 4	conventional group	care group	-.855 [*]	.273	.003	-1.407	-.303
	care group	conventional group	.855 [*]	.273	.003	.303	1.407
Functional reach test 5	conventional group	care group	-.890 [*]	.281	.003	-1.459	-.321
	care group	conventional group	.890 [*]	.281	.003	.321	1.459

RESULTS OF STUDY:

Descriptive analysis for demographics shows that age has a greater mean among groups A (conventional group) and B (care groups) than the other demographic variables, with 65 ± 4.815 and 66 ± 3.051 , respectively. Briefly, participants aged 63 and male patients have the highest frequency in both groups and majority are married persons. According to BMI, overweight participants have a larger frequency in conventional group while in care group obese participants have a count of numbers having waist circumference mostly in range of 44-51cm. Mostly participants have stage 2 hypertension in both groups with 70-79 bpm has a high frequency of heart rate and 15-17 breaths/min has high number of respiratory rate in both groups. Majority participants have saturation 97-98 % in both groups.

Group statistics results of Berg Balance Scale score of interventional group and conventional group shows that interventional group has higher mean values than conventional group. It shows that interventional group has low risk of fall than conventional group. After statistical analysis, Repeated Measure ANOVA test results of Berg Balance Scale score of interventional group and conventional group shows that both group has p-value less than .05 at all follow ups from baseline so difference with in the groups is significant. But mean values of interventional group are higher than the conventional group and it shows that participants of interventional group has lower risk of fall than conventional group participants. Comprehensive fall prevention protocol is better than conventional treatment.

In table 1.1 MANOVA test results of Berg Balance scale shows that difference between both groups i.e., conventional and interventional, is significant at all assessment levels (follow-ups) because p-value is less than .05 except at baseline where p-value is greater than .05 where no treatment is applied before. Similarly, Group Statistics of Functional Reach Test depicts that mean values are greater for interventional group as compared to conventional groups, which means on assessment of Functional Reach Test after each follow-up, participants of interventional group have lower risk of fall than conventional group.

According to statistical analysis, Repeated Measure ANOVA analysis for both groups (conventional and interventional) separately and results show that p-value for both groups is less than .05 which means in both groups there is significant difference of fall risk from baseline to all four follow-ups. So both group participants show low risk of fall but as mean values of interventional group participants are higher than conventional group so comprehensive fall protocol is more suitable to lowerrisk of fall than conventional protocol. In table 2.2, MANOVA analysis of Functional Reach Test shows that p-value is less than .05 which means there is significant difference between both groups and interventional group shows more significant results than conventional group. So comprehensive fall protocol is more significant than conventional treatment in reducing fall risk.

DISCUSSION:

This study was conducted to highlight the effects of comprehensive fall prevention protocol on fall risk in elderly population as compared to conventional treatment. Berg Balance Scale and Functional Reach Test were used as data collection tool to collect data from elderly population. All the participants were assessed at baseline before commencement of treatment and then after 4th, 8th, 12th and 24 week. There was significant improvement in both comprehensive fall prevention protocol group and conventional group. But improvement in comprehensive fall prevention group was more significant as compared to conventional group. so fall risk reduced more significantly in participants of comprehensive protocol group, also having less fear of fall, reduced incidence of injury and injury related consequences. For predicting the fall risk among elder population without any pathological condition, Berg Balance Scale along with Functional Reach Test were used in this study as both scales are effective parameters for fall risk prediction(25) because in a previous study it was suggested that Berg Balance Scale alone is not accurate tool for fall risk measurement in old age either with or without pathologies(23).

There was an evidence in previous study that exergaming is very effective in elder population regarding motor and psychological functions and it improves their quality of life as well as level of enjoyment, but that study not properly described any effect of this rehabilitation in reduction of fall risk. So in current study, exergaming was basically administered in fall prevention protocol (interventional protocol) to assess the reduction in fall in elder population with the help of Berg Balance Scale and Functional Reach Test(26). Comprehensive fall prevention protocol in current study included exergaming, which helped in reducing the fall risk among elders and showed significant results as compared to conventional group (exercise programs) at all follow-ups from baseline assessment(27). But a previous systematic review suggested that exercise programs (either individualized or grouped exercise programs) are also very effective in reducing falls and fall risk among elder populations(28).

CONCLUSION:

Comprehensive fall prevention protocol is very effective in improving balance in elderly population. Although both groups conventional and interventional show significant improvement at all follow-ups from baseline but comprehensive fall prevention protocol shows more prominent difference in reducing fall risk as compared to conventional treatment.

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